

Title:

Cleaning of contaminated MFM probes using a BOPP film and external magnetic field

Author names:

Chao Zhang^a, Jinyun Liu^{a,b}, Qingling Meng^a, Wenxiao Zhang^a, Ying Wang^a, Zuobin Wang^{a,b,*}

Affiliations:

^aJR3CN & CNM, Changchun University of Science and Technology, Changchun 130022, China

^bJR3CN & IRAC, University of Bedfordshire, Luton LU1 3JU, UK

Corresponding author:

Zuobin Wang, CNM & JR3CN, Changchun University of Science and Technology, Changchun 130022, China. Tel: +86 431 85582431; Fax: +86 431 85582925; e-mail: wangz@cust.edu.cn

Abstract

When testing magnetic samples with a magnetic force microscope (MFM), the probe tip can inevitably be contaminated and magnetic particles are often adhered to the surface of the tip. The probe with magnetic contamination will seriously affect the quality of morphology and magnetic imaging. In the work, a method for the cleaning of contaminated magnetic probe tips was developed by the use of a biaxially-oriented polypropylene (BOPP) film together with an external magnet field. In the experiment, an MFM system was used for manipulating the tip to push into the BOPP film with a depth of 50-100 nm under a magnetic field and hold for 5 seconds, and the relationships between the loading forces and the separating forces were studied. The scanning electron microscope (SEM) images have shown that the BOPP film together with an external magnet field is effective for the cleaning of contaminated MFM probes. This method can greatly improve the quality of magnetic imaging, prolong the service life of magnetic probes and reduce the experimental costs in many MFM applications.

Keywords:

Magnetic probe cleaning; Magnetic contamination; Biaxially-oriented polypropylene film; Magnetic field; Magnetic force microscope.

Introduction

The magnetic force microscope (MFM) is a powerful instrument used for the detecting of magnetic domain intensity and distribution of magnetic samples (Hartmann, 1990). MFM imaging is carried out by the detection of the force between

the magnetic probe and the sample (Zhu and Grutter, 2003; Wang *et al.*, 2015). In the MFM working mode, the two-pass scan strategy is applied to obtain the sample topography and magnetic images. During the first scan, the probe scans on the surface of sample with a tapping mode (Lin *et al.*, 2011; Eaton *et al.*, 2010) and then the probe is back to the beginning of current scan line with a constant lift height of 10-200 nm. During the second scan, the lift height is kept and the long-distance forces are obtained for imaging the magnetic structure by the detection of the changes of the probe cantilever vibration amplitude and phase according to the first scan profile.

Magnetic probes are usually coated with thin films such as Fe, Co and Ni that are sensitive to external magnetic fields and easily magnetized (Futamoto *et al.*, 2013; Amos *et al.*, 2012). In practice, MFMs are usually employed for the imaging and testing of magnetic samples. The accuracy of magnetic domain intensity distributions is closely related to the surface structure of the probe tip, and the tip determines the MFM resolution and the quality of scanned images (Liu *et al.*, 2012). In experiments, however, the probe tip can inevitably be contaminated and magnetic particles are often adhered to the tip surface. In this case, the probe magnetic contamination will reduce the quality of morphology and magnetic imaging, and the abandon of contaminated probes will increase the application costs (Philippe *et al.*, 2011).

In recent years, efforts have been made on the cleaning of contaminated MFM probes to deal with the magnetic contamination problems. There are currently four common methods developed for the cleaning of atomic force microscope (AFM) probes including the UV irradiation (Fang *et al.*, 2010; Kosoglu *et al.*, 2010), plasma

cleaning (Ponath *et al.*, 2013), ultrasonic cleaning (Troia *et al.*, 2008) and Nie methods (Nie *et al.*, 2002). The UV irradiation method is used to clean the tip contaminated by organic matter. Processing the contaminated tip with UV radiation can oxidize and decompose the organic contamination on the tip or cantilever, but it is only suitable for the cleaning of common organic contamination. The plasma cleaning method uses the plasma bombardment to clean the surface and the contamination is eventually removed by the vacuum pump. This method has the advantages of no chemical reaction and oxide on the sample surface, and the disadvantages that the plasma could damage the sample surface and produce the heat effect. The ultrasonic method can clean a number of contaminated probes at the same time in deionized water or cleaning agents using a proper ultrasonic power. The problem with this method is that it could cause a secondary contamination and damage the probes. The Nie method uses an organic thin film and pushes the probe into the film a few times to remove the contaminants adhered to the probe. This method has the advantage that the probe can be cleaned without moving the probe. However, all of the above methods are not suitable for the cleaning of the magnetically-contaminated magnetic probes.

In this work, a method of using a BOPP film together with an external magnetic field was developed for cleaning the magnetic contamination of MFM probe tips. In the experiment, an MFM system was used for the manipulating of the magnetic probe and study of the relationships between the loading forces and the separating forces, and a scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to observe the probe magnetic contaminants and cleaning results. The results have shown that the BOPP film

together with an external magnet field is effective for the cleaning of magnetically-contaminated MFM probes.

Theory

The Young's modulus of BOPP film was 2.2 GPa. It was far less than the silicon probe ranged from 132 GPa to 190 GPa (Lee and Rudd, 2007). Due to the good stretch property and the Young's modulus of BOPP film, it was suitable for the cleaning of contaminated probes and no damage was caused to the probe. In this work, a BOPP film together with an external magnetic field was used to clean the contaminated MFM probes.

There are mainly four types of adhesive forces between the MFM probe and the magnetic contaminants including the magnetic force, Van der Waals force, electrostatic force and capillary force. The mechanism and characteristic of each force are different, and the separation force should be larger than those adhesion forces to clean the contaminations from the magnetic probe.

Figure 1 shows the mechanical model of cleaning magnetic particles. In Figure 1, A is a BOPP film, B is a permanent magnet, F_1 is the resultant force between the magnetic particle and the probe, F_2 is the resultant force of the magnetic particle in the vertical downward direction during cleaning, Z is the vertical axis, β is the angle between F_1 and the Z axis, α_1 and α_2 are the angles viewed from the probe side with the centre line on the both sides, and $\alpha_2 > \alpha_1$. The angle of α_1 was 10 degrees and α_2 was 30 degrees.

Fig. 1. Mechanical model of cleaning magnetic particles.

The force between the magnetic particle and the probe can be written as

$$F_1 = F_{mg} + F_v + F_e + F_c \quad (1)$$

where F_{mg} is the magnetic force, F_v is the Van der Waals force, F_e is the electrostatic force and F_c is the capillary force. The component of F_1 in the Z axis can be computed by

$$F_z = F_1 \cos \beta = F_1 \cos(90 - \alpha_2) \quad (2)$$

The sum of adhesion forces in the Z direction can be expressed as

$$F_2 = G + M + F_a \quad (3)$$

where G is the gravity of the magnetic particle, M is the magnetic force from the magnet, and F_a is the adhesion force between the magnetic particle and the BOPP film. The magnetic contaminants can be adsorbed onto the BOPP film if $F_2 > F_z$, so that the parameter M in F_2 needs to be large enough. A high retentivity permanent magnet was used in the experiments. The experiments are described in the following sections.

Materials and Methods

Materials

A common BOPP film with a thickness of 25 μm was used as a sample. The density of the BOPP film was 0.91 g/cm^3 , the tensile strength in the machine direction was $\geq 125 \text{ MPa}$ and in the transverse direction was $\geq 220 \text{ MPa}$, and the Young's modulus in the machine direction was 2.2 GPa (Lepot *et al.*, 2011). A permanent magnet (NdFeB N52) with a retentivity of 12200 Gauss, diameter of 10 mm and thickness of 2 mm was used in the study. Fe_3O_4 magnetic particles with the diameter range from 50 nm to 100 nm were used as magnetic contaminants.

An MFM (JPK Nona Wizard) was used for the manipulation and measurement of the magnetic samples. The magnetic probe Magnetic Multi75-G (Budget Sensors) was used in the experiment. The resonant frequency of the magnetic probe was 75 kHz and the force constant was 3 N/m. The FEI QUANT-250 FEG SEM was used for observing the probe.

Methods

The probe cleaning process is shown in Figure 2. The BOPP film with a square size of $10 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$, which was pasted on the magnet and put on the sample stage, was used as a sample. Before pushing the tip into the BOPP film by manipulating the MFM, the contact mode was used for imaging the BOPP film to select a relatively flat area as the target. In the cleaning process, the probe was placed above the target area, as shown in Figure 2(a). The system parameters were adjusted to provide a loading

force on the probe to push the tip into the BOPP film with a depth of 50-100 nm and hold for 5 seconds, as shown in Figure 2(b), and finally the probe was lifted from the BOPP film, as shown in Figure 2(c). The procedure was repeated five times.

Fig. 2. Illustration of probe cleaning process. 1 is the sample stage, 2 is the permanent magnet, 3 is the BOPP film, 4 is the probe tip and 5 is the magnetic contamination.

Results and Discussions

The separation force and the adhesion force between the contaminated probe and the BOPP film and the magnet have been studied, and the force-distance curve of the contaminated probe pushing into the BOPP film is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that there is a jump of the cantilever at the height of 8.3 μm in the process of retract. It indicates that an attractive force was presented when the tip was separating from the surface of the BOPP film.

Fig. 3. Force-distance curve of the contaminated probe pushing into the BOPP film.

In the cleaning process, the magnetic particle and the probe are both affected by the permanent magnet. To study the adhesion force between the magnetic particles and the BOPP film, the relationships of the loading forces and the separating forces of the uncontaminated magnetic probe and contaminated magnetic probe were obtained, as shown in Figure 4.

In the experiment, different setpoint voltages were set to change the loading force of the cantilever. It can be seen that the separating forces are slowly increased with the rise of the loading force for the uncontaminated probe. Because of the good stretch property and the Young's modulus of BOPP film, the separating force from the BOPP film is larger than that from the magnet surface, and the separating force from the BOPP film together with the magnet is larger than that from the BOPP film because of the external magnetic force field. For a contaminated probe, separating forces are rapidly declined with the loading force increased from 0 nN to 50 nN which indicates that the magnetic particles are removed from the magnetic probe, and the

separating forces are changed slowly with the increase of the loading force from 50 nN to 300 nN. It can be observed that the separating forces obtained from the BOPP film together with the magnet are all rapidly declined, which demonstrates that the adhesion force between the magnetic contaminant and the BOPP film together with an external magnetic field is greater than the magnetic force between the magnetic contaminant and the probe surface.

Fig. 4. Relationships between the loading forces and the separating forces of the uncontaminated magnetic probe and the contaminated magnetic probe.

The cleaning results of a magnetically-contaminated MFM probe were observed by SEM, as shown in Figure 5. Figure 5(a) and Figure 5(b) show the results before and after the cleaning, respectively. It can be seen that the magnetically-contaminated MFM probe was well cleaned by the method of using the BOPP film together with the external magnet field.

Fig. 5. SEM images of the magnetically-contaminated MFM probes. (a) is the probe before the cleaning; (b) is the probe after the cleaning.

To identify the imaging capability after the cleaning of the magnetically-contaminated MFM probe, morphology images of magnetic particles and their corresponding magnetic images were obtained, as shown in Figure 6. It can be seen that the quality of the morphology image and magnetic image obtained with the cleaned MFM probe is significantly improved. It indicates that the BOPP film together with an external magnetic field is effective for cleaning the magnetically-contaminated MFM probe.

Fig. 6. MFM images of magnetic nanoparticles. (a) and (b) are the morphology and magnetic images obtained by a contaminated MFM probe; (c) and (d) are the morphology and magnetic images obtained by the MFM probe after the cleaning.

Conclusions

In this work, the method for the cleaning of magnetically contaminated MFM probes using a BOPP film and an external magnetic field has been presented. An MFM system was used in the experiment for manipulating the tip to push into the BOPP film with a depth of 50-100 nm under a magnetic field and hold for 5 seconds, and the relationships between the loading forces and the separating forces were obtained. A SEM was used to examine the contaminated MFM probe and its cleaning results. The experimental results have shown that this method is effective for the cleaning of magnetically contaminated MFM probes. It can greatly improve the quality of magnetic imaging, prolong the service life of magnetic probes and reduce the experimental costs in many MFM applications.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

References

- Hartmann, U., 1990. Theory of magnetic force microscopy. *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology, A* 8.1, 411-415.
- Zhu, X. B., Grutter, P., 2003. Magnetic force microscopy studies of patterned magnetic structures. *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, 39, 3420-3425.
- Wang, Y., et al., 2015. Differential magnetic force microscope imaging. *Scanning*, 37, 112-115.
- Lin, M. N., et al., 2011. Enhanced ferromagnetism in grain boundary of Co-doped ZnO films: a magnetic force microscopy study. *Applied Physics Letters*, 98, 212509-212509-3.
- Eaton, P. J., West, P., 2010. *Atomic force microscopy*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Futamato, M., et al., 2013. Fabrication of magnetic tips for high-resolution magnetic force microscopy. *Key Engineering Materials*, 543, 35-38.
- Amos, N., et al., 2012. Probes for enhanced magnetic force microscopy resolution, US Patent 8214918.
- Liu, F., et al., 2012. Characteristics of magnetic force microscopy magnetics on high moment perpendicular magnetic recording writers with high coercivity probes. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 111, 827-831.
- Philippe, T., et al., 2011. Mapping elasticity moduli of atherosclerotic plaque in situ via atomic force microscopy. *Journal of Structural Biology*, 174, 115-123.
- Fang, X., et al., 2010. A label-free immunosensor for diagnosis of dengue infection with simple electrical measurements. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 25, 1137-1142.
- Kosoglu, L. M., et al., 2010. Atomic force microscopy method for measuring smectite coefficients of friction. *Clays and Clay Minerals*, 58, 813-820.
- Ponath, P., et al., 2013. Preparation of a clean Ge (001) surface using oxygen plasma cleaning. *Journal of Vacuum Science & Technology B*, 31, 031201-031201-5.
- Troia, M. G., et al., 2008. The effect of surface modifications on titanium to enable titanium-porcelain bonding. *Dental Materials*, 24, 28-33.

- Nie, H. Y., et al., 2002. Use of biaxially oriented polypropylene film for evaluating and cleaning contaminated atomic force microscopy probe tips: an application to blind tip reconstruction. *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 73, 3831-3836.
- Lee, B., Rudd, R. E., 2007. First-principles study of the young's modulus of Si (001) nanowires. *Physical Review B*, 75, 041305.
- Lepot, N., et al., 2011. Influence of incorporation of ZnO nanoparticles and biaxial orientation on mechanical and oxygen barrier properties of polypropylene films for food packaging applications. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 120, 1616-1623.